

Diseases in rice fields in the Vietnamese Mekong delta, 1978 to 1980.^a

Disease	Causal agent	Important notes
Blast	<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i>	+++
Sheath blight	<i>Thanatephorus cucumeris</i>	+++
Bacterial blight	<i>Xanthomonas oryzae</i>	+++
Ufra	<i>Ditylenchus angustus</i>	+++
Rice ragged stunt	Virus, vector <i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	+++ → ±
Brown spot	<i>Cochliobolus miyabeanus</i>	++
Kernel smut	<i>Tilletia barclayana</i>	+++ → ±
Bakanae	<i>Gibberella fujikuroi</i>	++ → ±
Bacterial leaf streak	<i>X. translucens</i> var. <i>oryzicola</i>	++ → ±
Narrow brown leaf spot	<i>Sphaerulina oryzae</i>	+
Akagare type II	H ₂ S toxicity	+
Root knot nematode	<i>Meloidogyne</i> sp.	+
Leaf spot	<i>Curvularia lunata</i>	±
Acid sulfate soil toxicity	Fe, Al toxicity, and P deficiency	+
False smut	<i>Ustilagoideia virens</i>	±
Sheath rot	<i>Acrocyndrium oryzae</i>	±
Stem rot	<i>Helminthosporium sigmoideum</i>	±
Stem rot	<i>H. sigmoideum</i> var. <i>irregularare</i>	±
Minute leaf spot	<i>Nigrospora oryzae</i>	±
Stackburn disease	<i>Trichoconis padwickii</i>	±
Small leaf blight	<i>Phyllosticta glumarum</i>	±
Leaf smut	<i>Entyloma oryzae</i>	±
Sheath blotch	<i>Pyrenochaeta oryzae</i>	±
Seedling blight	<i>Botryobasidium rolfsii</i>	±
Bacterial sheath rot	<i>Pseudomonas oryzicola</i>	±
Grassy stunt	Mycoplasma (?)	±
Rice stripe (?)	(?)	±
Orange leaf (?)	(?)	±

^a± light, + medium, ++ heavy, +++ severe, (?) not yet determined.

than 10% diseased grain was observed in some fields in the center of the area.

Rice ragged stunt also broke out severely in 1978 together with the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* epidemic and concentrated in the north-eastern part of the delta.

Bacterial sheath rot (*Pseudomonas*

oryzicola) and seedling blight (*Botryobasidium rolfsii*) were first discovered in the delta in 1978 and 1979.

Fungi on stored grain were *Penicillium* sp., *Aspergillus* sp., *Trichoconis padwickii*, *Gibberella fujikuroi*, *Helminthosporium oryzae*, and *Curvularia lunata*. ■

1. Distribution of regions with severe rice blast the Vietnamese Mekong delta, 1978-80.

2. Distribution of regions with severe sheath blight in the Vietnamese Mekong delta, 1978-80.

Variability in the incidence of udbatta disease on paddy rice varieties in Karnataka State, India, 1978-80

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Udbatta disease (caused by *Ephelis oryzae*) has occurred in Karnataka State for a long time. A fairly high incidence was noticed recently on some high-yielding varieties of paddy rice. In a diseased plant, the entire panicle is infected and incidence in even a single panicle results in 100% loss. This 3-year study was conducted to determine disease incidence in 20 selected paddy rice cultures.

Incidence of udbatta disease in 20 selected rice cultures in Karnataka State, India, 1978-80.

The average disease incidence (see figure) among cultures varied from 4% in IET2295 to 22% in IET3626. The

data indicate a narrow range of variability in disease incidence in the varieties, except in IET3626. ■